

Overview

This code replicates the results obtained in the paper “No alarms and no surprises: dynamics of renewable energy curtailment in California”. It consists of an R script “Curtailment_replication.R” originally run in a Windows 10 x86-64 machine. We also provide an additional R script called “stargazer_betareg.R”, which is only necessary to create the regression table (it modifies the original stargazer call to make it work with Pearson residuals in the beta regression). This README file is structured into the following sections: Section 1 provides an overview of the data. Section 2 explains how to replicate the results and Section 3 provides additional system information.

1. Data Availability

1.1. Input data

The data sources used in this study are the following (all links working on 2022-11-15):

1. Hourly production and curtailment data provided by the California Independent System Operator (CAISO), publicly available at

<http://www.caiso.com/informed/Pages/ManagingOversupply.aspx>

2. Monthly small-scale PV production by the Energy Information Administration of the USA (EIA), Form EIA-861M (formerly EIA-826), publicly available at

<https://www.eia.gov/electricity/data/eia861m/>

3. Yearly battery storage capacities and applications, by the EIA, Form EIA-860 detailed data with previous form data (EIA-860A/860B)

<https://www.eia.gov/electricity/data/eia860/>

4. Hourly day-ahead wholesale electricity prices, by CAISO, publicly available for the last three years at the OASIS platform

<http://oasis.caiso.com/mrioasis/logon.do>

5. Past and projected PV and wind and installation costs, by the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), publicly available at

<https://www.irena.org/publications/2019/Oct/Future-of-wind>

<https://www.irena.org/publications/2019/Nov/Future-of-Solar-Photovoltaic>

6. Levelized cost of storage reports by Lazard, publicly available at

<https://www.lazard.com/perspective/levelized-cost-of-energy-levelized-cost-of-storage-and-levelized-cost-of-hydrogen/>

The raw data can be accessed on the links above and cleaned with the code provided in the attached R script. The clean data is provided as follows:

Data	File	Source
Curtailment	curtailment.rds	CAISO (1)
Production	production.rds	CAISO (1)
Curtailment and production, including also small scale PV	curt_input.rds	CAISO (1) + EIA (2)
Storage capacities and apps.	storage.rds	EIA (3)
Day-ahead wholesale prices	prices_xts.rds	CAISO (4)
Wind and PV cost	cost.xlsx	IRENA (5)

1.2. Results

We also provide results data directly as follows:

Data	File
Linear regression results (list)	regresults_logit.rds
Linear regression results (dataframe)	allregresults.rds
Augmented Dickey–Fuller tests	adftable.rds
Phillips–Perron test	pptable.rds
Variance inflation factors	vif.rds
BAM models	Bammodels.rds
GAM models	Gammodels.rds
Concurvity	Concur.rds

Finally, a folder is also provided with the resulting figures.

2. Instructions to Replicators

There are two R scripts: “Curtailment_replication.R” where all the necessary code for the analysis is contained, and “stargazer_betareg.R”, which is only necessary to create the main regression table. The raw data are too big and publicly available, so we do not explicitly include it in this replication package. However, it can be downloaded on the links provided on Section 1 and cleaned according to the code provided in the main R script. We provide the cleaned data to run the analysis and the results generated during the analysis.

The main R script “Curtailment_replication.R” is divided into the following sections:

Introduction: first the working directory is set with `setwd(“...”)`, please, change the working directory to the address of your local folder where you downloaded the

replication files. The necessary packages are loaded as well as some other useful functions created by the authors.

1. **Import:** this section imports and cleans the data. Most of this section is commented out because the cleaned data is directly provided. This commented out code explains the cleaning process from the raw data.
2. **Exploratory:** present the main data, including summary statistics and the figures in the data section of the paper
3. **Reg:** main regression analysis, subdivided into three sections: OLS, Prais-Winsten and beta, and including the visualization, regression tables and robustness analyses.
4. **GAMS:** generalized additive models analysis including tables and visualizations
5. **LCOE:** impact of curtailment on wind and solar LCOE
6. **Storage profit:** last analysis of the paper comparing peak wholesale prices with the levelized cost of storage.

3. Computational requirements

Some processes are computationally heavy, particularly the generalized additive models. Running the code can take from minutes to hours depending on the machine. Details on the session information can be found below:

R version 3.6.2 (2019-12-12)

Platform: x86_64-w64-mingw32/x64 (64-bit)

Running under: Windows 10 x64 (build 19045)

Matrix products: default

locale:

```
[1] LC_COLLATE=English_United Kingdom.1252 LC_CTYPE=English_United Kingdom.1252
```

```
[3] LC_MONETARY=English_United Kingdom.1252 LC_NUMERIC=C
```

```
[5] LC_TIME=English_United Kingdom.1252
```

attached base packages:

```
[1] splines stats4 grid stats graphics grDevices utils datasets methods base
```

other attached packages:

```
[1] ggribges_0.5.3 ggrepel_0.9.1 strucchange_1.5-2 betareg_3.1-4 forecast_8.14
```

[6] metR_0.12.0 viridis_0.6.2 viridisLite_0.4.0 aTSA_3.1.2 stargazer_5.2.2
 [11] prais_1.1.2 pcse_1.9.1.1 urca_1.3-0 regclass_1.6 randomForest_4.6-14
 [16] rpart_4.1-15 VGAM_1.1-5 bestglm_0.37.3 leaps_3.1 scales_1.1.1
 [21] gridExtra_2.3 tidymv_3.3.0 mgcv_1.8-35 nlme_3.1-152 tidyselect_1.1.2
 [26] magrittr_2.0.2 anytime_0.3.9 xts_0.12.1 lmtest_0.9-38 zoo_1.8-9
 [31] modelsummary_0.9.6 broom_0.7.12 sandwich_3.0-1 car_3.0-12
 carData_3.0-5
 [36] readxl_1.3.1 datetime_0.1.4 lubridate_1.8.0 fixest_0.8.4 forcats_0.5.1
 [41] stringr_1.4.0 dplyr_1.0.8 purrr_0.3.3 readr_2.1.2 tidyr_1.2.0
 [46] tibble_3.1.6 ggplot2_3.3.5 tidyverse_1.3.1

loaded via a namespace (and not attached):

[1] colorspace_1.4-1 modeltools_0.2-23 ellipsis_0.3.2 pls_2.8-0 fs_1.5.0
 [6] rstudioapi_0.13 flexmix_2.3-17 fansi_0.4.1 xml2_1.3.3 codetools_0.2-18
 [11] knitr_1.37 Formula_1.2-4 jsonlite_1.8.0 dbplyr_2.1.1 compiler_3.6.2
 [16] httr_1.4.2 backports_1.1.5 assertthat_0.2.1 Matrix_1.3-3 fastmap_1.1.0
 [21] cli_3.2.0 htmltools_0.5.2 tools_3.6.2 gtable_0.3.0 glue_1.6.2
 [26] dreamerr_1.2.3 tables_0.9.6 Rcpp_1.0.3 cellranger_1.1.0 fracdiff_1.5-1
 [31] vctrs_0.3.8 iterators_1.0.14 grpreg_3.3.1 timeDate_3043.102 xfun_0.29
 [36] rvest_1.0.2 lifecycle_1.0.1 pacman_0.5.1 hms_1.1.1 parallel_3.6.2
 [41] curl_4.3.1 quantmod_0.4.18 rpart.plot_3.1.0 stringi_1.6.1 tseries_0.10-48
 [46] foreach_1.5.2 checkmate_2.0.0 TTR_0.24.2 shape_1.4.6 rlang_1.0.1
 [51] pkgconfig_2.0.3 lattice_0.20-44 plyr_1.8.6 R6_2.5.1 generics_0.1.2
 [56] DBI_1.1.2 pillar_1.7.0 haven_2.4.3 withr_2.4.3 survival_3.2-11
 [61] abind_1.4-5 nnet_7.3-16 modelr_0.1.8 crayon_1.5.0 utf8_1.1.4
 [66] tzdb_0.2.0 data.table_1.14.2 reprex_2.0.1 digest_0.6.29
 numDeriv_2016.8-1.1
 [71] munsell_0.5.0 glmnet_4.1-1 quadprog_1.5-8